

IMPACT OF IMPRESSION MANAGEMENT TACTICS ON GEN Z'S TURNOVER INTENTION: MEDIATING ROLE OF PERSON- ORGANIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the factors influencing Gen Z employees' intention to stay in their organizations is crucial in today's competitive job market. This study examines the relationship between Impression Management tactics, Work Adjustment Theory, and their combined impact on employee retention in Islamabad. The five identified Impression Management tactics—Employee Ingratiation, Employee Self-Promotion, Exemplification, Intimidation, and Supplication—are analyzed for their effects on workplace perceptions and behaviors. By incorporating Work Adjustment Theory, we explore how individuals adapt to their work environments and how these adaptations correlate with successful employment outcomes. Our findings reveal that Impression Management tactics positively influence Perceived Person-Organization Fit, which in turn negatively affects employees' turnover intentions. The mediating role of Perceived Person-Organization Fit is crucial in understanding these dynamics. Using a quantitative, cross-sectional approach, data were collected from Generation Z professionals in the telecom sector through convenience sampling. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was employed to analyze the relationships among the identified variables. This comprehensive exploration provides insights into the workplace strategies and adaptations of Generation Z employees, offering valuable implications for organizational management practices. The results underscore the importance of Impression Management in fostering alignment between employees and their organizations, ultimately reducing employees' turnover intention.

Keywords: Impression Management, Perceived Person-Organization Fit, Turnover Intention, Generation Z.

INTRODUCTION

The modern workplace is a complex blend of different generations, each contributing their unique perspectives and experiences (Sobrinho-De Toro, Labrador-Fernandez, & De Nicolas, 2019). Among the newest members of the workforce, Generation Z, also known as Gen Z, stands out for its digital proficiency and the unique challenges it brings to the professional world.

Generation Z and millennials share many similarities, but they may differ in management style, teamwork, social interactions, and motivation, which can lead to conflicts (Gabrielova & Buchko, 2021). Previous generations, such as baby boomers, Generation X, and millennials, have received considerable attention from researchers in the field of human

resource development (Chaudhuri & Ghosh, 2012).

As Generation Z enters the workforce, organizations must understand the characteristics of this newest generation to effectively address the diverse needs of all employees (Perilus, 2020). For this reason, the new generation may use impression management tactics (Edeh et al., 2023) to demonstrate to their managers that they are the perfect fit for the organization. In recent years, an increasing number of researchers, such as Grow & Yang (2018) and Liu, Chow, & Huang (2019), have examined impression management (IM), indicating that scholars are concentrating on understanding how employees attempt to control the perceptions of others. Regarding preferred values and thought patterns at work, there are both similarities and differences between generations, with the youngest generation being the most other-directed and possessing the least developed personal standards of judgment (Kwiecińska, Grzesik, Siewierska-Chmaj, & Popielska-Borys, 2023). Exploring the dynamics of Gen Z's entry into the workplace reveals a complex web of factors that affect their ability to remain engaged and committed (Bierbrier, 2022). According to Heyns and Kerr (2018), these connections are evolving, and this evolution significantly affects Generation Z's motivation in the workplace. In the age of social media and connectivity, Gaidhani, Arora, and Sharma (2019) emphasize that Gen Z actively navigates their presence in both realms, recognizing how it can influence their relationships within the workplace. Maloni, Hiatt, and Campbell (2019) demonstrate that the work values of Generation Z differ significantly from those of older generations, highlighting the necessity to adapt the organizational work environment to meet the unique needs of Generation Z.

Within research on organizational behavior and employee dynamics, the key work of Edeh et al. (2023) stands out as a focal point, centering on the profound influence of impression management on employee contextual performance. This underscores the need for further investigations into additional factors that could contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of how impression management affects employees' attitudes. Gabrielova and Buchko (2021) discussed the conflicts that arise between Millennials and Gen Z, suggesting that

employees themselves hold the answers to questions regarding the management of Generation Z. While we recognize the unique characteristics and motivations of Gen Z, as well as the importance of employee retention, there remains a gap in understanding how their relationships with managers—such as impression management tactics and perceived person-organization fit—affect their decision to stay (Omilion-Hodges & Ptacek, 2021).

Literature Review:

Impression Management

Impression Management theory, also known as self-presentation theory, is a sociological and psychological concept that explores how individuals actively work to control the impressions others form of them. Goffman (1949) compares social interactions to theatrical performances, where individuals play the role of performers and the social context serves as the stage. He introduces the concept of "impression management," which refers to the conscious and subconscious efforts individuals make to present themselves in a favorable light, shaping the perceptions others have of them. It provides a theoretical foundation for understanding how individuals strategically manage impressions, aligning well with the impression management tactics outlined in your model. Later on, Jones and Pittman (1982) proposed five strategies for impression management: Self-Promotion, Ingratiation, Exemplification, Intimidation, and Supplication. The choice of a specific strategy depends on the kind of impression the first party wants to create in the eyes of the second party. Importantly, these strategies are not mutually exclusive, meaning the first party can use one or more of these strategies simultaneously to influence how the second party feels and perceives the situation. In other words, individuals have the flexibility to employ various strategies based on their goals to shape how others see them.

Impression management

Impression management refers to how individuals present themselves to others to garner likability or acceptance. They seek to create a positive impression and conform to others' expectations. People intentionally emphasize certain traits or aspects of themselves that they believe will endear them to others (Moritz & Bartz-Beielstein, 2017).

Applicant ingratiation and applicant self-promotion are positively related to perceived P-O fit. Employees often engage in impression management strategies to cultivate a favorable image of themselves as competent, likable, or exemplary workers (Krieg et al., 2018). At the same time, other individuals may strive to project an image of authority or, conversely, portray themselves as vulnerable and in need of assistance (Xiao et al., 2024). These cultivated images provide various benefits to the individuals who deploy them, such as greater acceptance, favorable performance evaluations, and higher ratings of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Krieg et al., 2018).

Impression management techniques are typically divided into positive and negative categories (Bolino et al., 2016). Within the spectrum of positive tactics, literature identifies self-promotion, ingratiation, and exemplification as key strategies (Bierbrier, 2022; Haber, 2017; Payne et al., 2021). Self-promotion focuses on creating an image of competence by emphasizing one's achievements, contributions, and successes within the workplace (Den Hart et al., 2020; Molleman, 2019). Ingratiation aims to enhance personal attractiveness by currying favor with others through expressions of approval, praise, gifts, and favors (Bande et al., 2019). Exemplification involves actions designed to showcase oneself as a role model through dedication and exerting more effort than might be strictly necessary (Hart et al., 2020; Long, 2017).

Conversely, the literature categorizes tactics such as intimidation and supplication as negative impression management strategies (Chawla et al., 2021; Su et al., 2014). Intimidation tactics are employed to project power and instill a perception of the actor as threatening or formidable (Kimura et al., 2018; Azeem, 2024). This approach may serve to establish a self-identity rooted in power dynamics that can influence others' perceptions and interactions. On the other hand, supplication involves presenting oneself as helpless to elicit sympathy and support from others (Stanley et al., 2020). This tactic plays on the compassionate instincts of the target to gain aid or concessions that might not otherwise be offered.

Ingratiation as an impression management tactic

Soojin Lee, Han, Cheong, Kim, and Yun (2017) found in their recent research that individuals utilize an ingratiation strategy, also known as

attraction management, to achieve the social acceptance they desire. Ingratiation employs tactics such as doing favors or offering flattery to garner admiration and present oneself as likable to others. When used judiciously, ingratiation proves to be a successful means of influencing others (Chao et al., 2013). Essentially, it involves identifying the qualities believed to be attractive by the audience and adjusting one's behavior accordingly. Therefore, we assume that employees' use of the ingratiation tactic in an organization with their employers positively affects their person-organization fit.

Self-promotion as an impression management tactic:

Individuals who self-promote may come across as arrogant, especially when they boast about their actions and skills to people who lack knowledge or evidence to verify the accuracy of these claims (Jones & Pittman, 1982). When employees use self-promotion tactics, they are basically showing off their good qualities, talking about their plans for the future, or mentioning their past accomplishments. It is a way for them to make sure others notice the positive things about them and understand their value at work (Gross et al., 2021). Self-promotion plays a crucial role in shaping the perceived person-organization fit, particularly concerning co-worker support (Edeh et al., 2023). Therefore, we assume employees' use of self-promotion tactic in an organization with their employers positively affect their person-organization fit.

Exemplification as an impression management tactic:

When presented with the chance to be viewed as exemplary employees, individuals engage in an exemplification strategy by setting higher standards and going above and beyond the call of duty (Crawford, Kacmar, & Harris, 2019). An exemplifier wants everyone to think they are a hard worker and are willing to make sacrifices (Jones & Pittman, 1982). So, we think that when employees use the exemplification tactic at work, it makes them feel like they fit well into the organization.

Supplication as an impression management tactic

Supplementation is used by people with disabilities who cannot easily perform regular

activities. They talk about their weaknesses to create a social rule that says others should help them (Rosenfeld, Edwards, & Thomas, 2015). Overall, supplication is seen as a quiet strategy to get support and help from others (Lim, Chidambaram, & Carte, 2008). So, it can be concluded that when employees use supplication in an organization, it might result in a poor perceived person-organization fit.

Intimidation as an Impression Management Tactic

An intimidator works to gain social power by convincing others that they are a dangerous and powerful force (Jones & Pittman, 1982). This strategy involves creating an image of credibility regarding the intimidator's capacity for danger and threats. The goal is to increase the likelihood that the people they are targeting will comply with their demands and behave in a certain way (Riess, Rosenfeld, Melburg, & Tedeschi, 1981). In essence, it is about making others perceive them as a profound and potent influence to get what they want.

Perceived person-organization fit

How well a person's values match with their organization, called P-O fit, can be looked at in two ways. One is about how well an individual thinks their values align with the organization's values (subjective P-O fit). The other is about how well others think the individual's values match the organization's values (objective P-O fit). We measure P-O fit directly (individuals say how well their values match the organization's values) or indirectly (individuals rate their values and the organization's values separately). Even though P-O fit can also include things like personality or skills, we focus on perceived P-O fit, directly measuring how individuals see the match between their values and the organization's. We do this because people feel more positive when they believe there is a good fit (Cable & Edwards, 2004; Chi & Pan, 2011).

Perceived P-O fit is connected to positive outcomes like being happy with the job and behaving well in the organization. It is also linked to lower intentions to leave the job (Abdalla, Elsetouhi, Negm, & Abdou, 2018; Kristof-Brown et al., 2023).

The ASA model suggests that people are more interested in joining organizations that are similar

to them. At the same time, organizations want to pick individuals who are like the others already in the organization and share similar values and goals. The process of people joining and leaving the organization helps make the environment more similar because those who fit well stay, while those who do not leave (Pressley et al., 1987).

Turnover Intention

Employee turnover is a big deal for companies because it comes with many costs. When employees leave, the organization has to pay for things like severance pay, finding and training new people, and dealing with the difference in performance between those leaving and the new ones coming in (Stamolampros, Korfiatis, Chalvatzis, & Buhalis, 2019). Mussie Tessema, Tesfom, Faircloth, Tesfagiorgis, and Teckle (2022) proposed the idea that an organization's overall effectiveness may face adverse consequences when experiencing frequent resignations.

Researchers found positive relationships among perceived person-organization fit (P-O fit), perceived person-group fit (P-G fit), and perceived person-job fit (P-J fit). These fits were negatively associated with turnover intention (TI). Gen Z individuals are digital natives, having grown up in an era of rapid technological advancements, making them highly reliant on mobile devices and internet connectivity for communication, entertainment, and work (Bhalla, Tiwari, & Chowdhary, 2021). Therefore, studying Gen Z's interaction with telecom services can provide insights into emerging trends and preferences in the industry. Secondly, Gen Z employees bring unique characteristics and expectations to the workplace, which can impact organizational dynamics and performance (Kodithuwakku, Jusoh, & Chinna, 2018). Research on Gen Z employees in the telecom sector can shed light on their career aspirations, job satisfaction drivers, and factors influencing retention (Zahari & Puteh, 2023). Understanding Gen Z's perspective on workplace culture, career development opportunities, and work-life balance is crucial for telecom companies to attract and retain top talent in a competitive market (Rodríguez-Sánchez, González-Torres, Montero-Navarro, & Gallego-Losada, 2020). Furthermore, Gen Z's influence extends beyond their demographic cohort, as they often play a significant role in influencing purchasing decisions within their families and

social networks (Silva, Machado, & Cruz, 2017). Research on Gen Z's consumer behavior in the telecom sector can help companies develop targeted marketing strategies and product offerings that resonate with this influential demographic group (Salam, Singkeruang, Husni, Baharuddin, & AR, 2024). It has been observed that when ingratiation efforts fail to yield the expected rewards, employees may perceive this as unfair treatment, which can subsequently trigger counterproductive work behaviors (Guglielmi, Mazzetti, Villano, & Topa Cantisano, 2018). This perception arises from the belief that their efforts to please and gain favor have not been appropriately acknowledged or rewarded, leading to frustration and potential workplace discord. Moreover, studies have identified a positive correlation between ingratiation behaviors and the likelihood of engaging in counterproductive actions within the workplace (Yang et al., 2021). These individuals are less likely to use threats or coercion as a means of gaining power. Therefore, we propose that employees using ingratiation tactics with their supervisors positively influence their perceived person-organization fit.

H1a: Gen Z employees' ingratiation has a positive impact on perceived P-O fit.

Participative management encourages interaction and cooperation between staff and leadership. Top-level managers leverage self-promotion to influence their subordinates by highlighting their diligence, accomplishments since assuming leadership, and the skills necessary for success in their roles, as discussed in studies by Shayaa et al. (2018) and Bigliardi, Ferraro, Filippelli, and Galati (2021). This strategic display of competence and achievement helps solidify their credibility and authority within the organization. Recent research, such as Guohao et al. (2021), challenges previous assumptions by showing that using ingratiation techniques can improve performance. Coworker support is fostered not only by supervisors' self-promotion but also by employees' adoption of these behaviors (Shayaa et al., 2018). Therefore, we propose that employees using self-promotion tactics with their supervisors positively influence their perceived person-organization fit.

H1b: Gen Z employees' self-promotion has a positive impact on perceived P-O fit.

Employees' exemplification has a positive impact on employees' contextual performance (Edeh, 2018). Employees often strive to positively influence their managers, imitating the behaviors they observe in higher-level executives to climb the organizational ladder (Kawiana et al., 2018). The technique of exemplification, which includes actions like working overtime, indirectly boosts individual performance by making supervisors more favorable towards these self-sacrificing employees (Bande, Kimura, Fernández-Ferrín, Castro-González, & Goel, 2023). Furthermore, according to the affect-consistency bias theory proposed by Guo et al. (2021), the positive feelings a supervisor holds towards an employee play a crucial role in securing favorable performance evaluations, particularly when the employee engages in exemplification behaviors.

H1c: Gen Z employees' exemplification has a positive impact on perceived P-O fit.

On the negative side, intimidation and supplication tactics are less studied and often seen as detrimental (Bolino et al., 2016; McGowan & Sekaja, 2022). Intimidation is used to project power and induce fear, though its impact on performance is generally negative (Chawla et al., 2021; Kimura, Bande, & Fernandez-Ferrín, 2018). Supplication, which portrays the actor as needy, has yielded mixed performance outcomes, both positive and negative (Chawla et al., 2021; Cheng, Chiu, & Tzeng, 2013).

Thus, the following hypothesis can be predicted;

H1d: Gen Z employees' intimidation has a positive impact on perceived P-O fit. H1e: Gen Z employees' supplication has a positive impact on perceived P-O fit.

Research findings consistently highlight a prevalent issue within modern workplaces: a significant number of employees feel unsupported by their organizations, resulting in heightened levels of job dissatisfaction and increased turnover rates (Hirsch-Kreinsen & Ittermann, 2021). This dissatisfaction stems from various challenges that employees face,

Ranging from difficulties in achieving a satisfactory work-life balance to accessing effective employee assistance programs (ValeVale) and engaging in meaningful virtual socialization and networking

opportunities (Sammer, Sammer, & Donnelly, 2019). Additionally, concerns about inadequate employee wellness programs (Knani, Fournier, & Biron, 2021), insufficient IT support and training for remote work arrangements (Mark, Kun, Rintel, & Sellen, 2022), and ineffective management practices (Triana, Gu, Chapa, Richard, & Colella, 2021) further worsen employees' discontent.

Furthermore, employees encounter shortcomings in critical areas such as the provision of personal protective equipment and maintaining a safe work environment (Sheather & Slattery, 2021), access to sufficient paid leave (Ferrara, Garofalo, & Agovino, 2020), and opportunities to express grievances (Wang, Dilmore, Bacon, & Harbert, 2021). These factors collectively contribute to a pervasive sense of dissatisfaction among employees, ultimately influencing their decision to resign from their positions (Hirsch-Kreinsen & Ittermann, 2021).

Given the significant impact of HR policies and practices on job satisfaction and employee turnover, there is an urgent need for organizations to adopt effective HR strategies. Progressive HR approaches are not only essential for enhancing job satisfaction but also for reducing employee turnover rates (Mussie T Tessema et al., 2022). Organizations that successfully address these HR challenges are better positioned to thrive and succeed in an increasingly competitive global market. Therefore, prioritizing the development and implementation of effective HR policies is crucial for businesses seeking to retain talent and maintain a competitive edge in today's dynamic workplace landscape.

H2: Perceived P-O fit has a negative impact on Gen Z employee turnover intention. H3a: Employee Ingratiation has a negative impact on employee turnover intention.

H3b: Employee Self-promotion has a negative impact on employee turnover intention.

H3c: Employee Exemplification has a negative impact on employee turnover intention.

H3d: Employee Intimidation has a negative impact on employee turnover intention. H3e: Employee Supplication has a negative impact on employee turnover intention.

Chawla et al. (2021) conducted a detailed study on the effects of integrating both positive and negative impression-management tactics. Their findings suggest that the impact of these behaviors

on performance outcomes is multifaceted and significantly influenced by the employee's adeptness in employing these tactics effectively. These tactics serve distinct purposes: self-promotion is used to project competence, ingratiation to foster likability and kindness, and exemplification to demonstrate commitment and diligence (Vale, Stanley, Houston, Villalba, & Turner, 2020). The effectiveness of self-promotion and exemplification on actual job performance has presented varied results, with some studies reporting them as less effective (Crawford et al., 2019; Gross et al., 2021). In contrast, the benefits of ingratiation in enhancing performance levels have been consistently supported by empirical evidence (Haber, 2017). Conversely, the use of negative tactics such as intimidation and supplication has been less explored and is often associated with adverse outcomes (Bolino et al., 2016; McGowan & Sekaja, 2022). Intimidation is typically used to create an image of power and induce fear among colleagues, but studies suggest that it negatively impacts task performance (Chawla et al., 2021; Kimura et al., 2018).

H4a: Perceived P-O fit mediates the relationship between Gen Z Employee Ingratiation and Turnover intention.

H4b: Perceived P-O fit mediates the relationship between Gen Z Employee Self-promotion and Turnover intention.

H4c: Perceived P-O fit mediates the relationship between Gen Z Employee Exemplification and Turnover intention.

H4d: Perceived P-O fit mediates the relationship between Gen Z Employee Intimidation and Turnover intention.

H4e: Perceived P-O fit mediates the relationship between Gen Z Employee Supplication and Turnover intention.

Research Methodology

This research focuses on quantitative research, a cross-sectional study as it is carried out at one point at a time. This type of survey involves the utilization of a questionnaire to gather data concurrently from numerous participants situated in the same geographic location (Bell, Bryman, & Harley, 2022).

In this research, respondents are Generation Z employees in the telecom industry located in Islamabad. The anticipated expansion of the

Pakistan Telecom Market indicates a projected increase from USD 4.38 billion in 2023 to USD 5.15 billion by 2028, reflecting a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 3.28% throughout the forecast period (2023-2028).³ Questionnaires will be distributed to them to gather insights based on their work settings and their own perception.

Measurement and scales

The proposed study is a self-administered study. So, the scales of the variables under research are adopted from the previous studies. (Abdalla et al., 2018; Benton et al., 2020; M. Bolino et al., 2016; Bolino & Turnley, 1999; Cable & DeRue, 2002; Hamstra, Van Vianen, & Koen, 2019). The items of the variables are measured on the 5-point Likert scale, which will help to investigate the relationship of Impression management tactics and Gen Z's intention to stay in the organization with a mediating role of perceived person organization fit. The first part of the questionnaire consists of the demographic information while the second part includes the constructs of the variables which will investigate the study.

Impression management tactics

To assess impression management tactics, the scales formulated by (M. C. Bolino & Turnley, 1999) will be employed. Gen-Z employees will be requested to evaluate the frequency of their utilization of impression management tactics. Recent researches that measured Impression management tactics used this scale (Benton et al., 2020; Edeh et al., 2023; Khizar et al., 2020).

Perceived person-organization fit

To assess perceived person organization fit, the scale formulated by Cable & DeRue, 2002. Sample item is "There is a good fit between what my job offers me and what I am looking for in a job" was employed using Five-point Likert scale with

responses ranging from 1 "Strongly Agree" to 5 "Strongly disagree" in the questionnaire. Recent researches that measured perceived person-organization fit used this scale (Abdalla et al., 2018; Hamstra et al., 2019)

Turnover Intention

To assess turnover intention, the scale formulated by (Seashore, Lawler III, Mirvis, & Cammann, 1983). Sample item is "It is likely that I will actively look for a new organization to work for in the next year" was employed using Five-point Likert scale, with responses ranging from 1 "Strongly Agree" to 5 "Strongly disagree" in the questionnaire. Recent researches that measured turnover intention used this scale (Abdalla et al., 2018).

Quantitative data is collected from a large number of people that fit a certain criterion of the respective study. The results gathered from this type of data can be generalized (Apuke, 2017). Quantitative data is collected from a large number of people that fit a certain criterion of the respective study. Primary data was collected by sending questionnaires; online as well as offline. Data was collected from Generation Z employees in Islamabad.

Results:

Collinearity

Collinearity of the data is defined as the independent or predictor variables are highly correlated to each other. In other words, they are considered as similar variables rather than different variables. Collinearity is determined in two ways. The first is by analyzing the correlation between independent variables. Secondly by analyzing the Variance Inflation method (VIF). If the correlation between the independent variables is equal to +1 that means there is high collinearity between variables. The following table shows that there is no collinearity between independent variables.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

	EXEM	INGRAT	INTIM	PPOF	SELFPRO	SUPP	TI
EXEM	1	0.275	0.444	0.448	0.359	0.202	-0.242
INGRAT	0.275	1	0.296	0.502	0.215	0.246	-0.323
INTIM	0.444	0.296	1	0.476	0.297	0.358	-0.325
PPOF	0.448	0.502	0.476	1	0.33	0.374	-0.57
SELFPRO	0.359	0.215	0.297	0.33	1	0.157	-0.177
SUPP	0.202	0.246	0.358	0.374	0.157	1	-0.276
TI	-0.242	-0.323	-0.325	-0.57	-0.177	-0.276	1

Before assessing any statistical relationships, we need to assess collinearity needs to avoid any kind of biases that might occur in regression results. This is ensured by the Variance inflation factor. Studies like Hair, Hollingsworth, Randolph, and Chong (2017) have mentioned that the acceptable range of VIF values is between 1 to 10. If the

value is closer to 1 that means there is either little or no collinearity and if the VIF value is closer to 10 it means that they have high collinearity (Neter & Ben-Shakhar, 1989). All the values mentioned in the table are closer to 1, which shows there is no collinearity among them.

Table 3: collinearity Statistics - VIF Inner-Model - Matrix

	EXEM	INGRAT	INTIM	PPOF	SELFPRO	SUPP	TI
EXEM				1.366			1.437
INGRAT				1.164			1.354
INTIM				1.43			1.504
PPOF							1.799
SELFPRO				1.193			1.212
SUPP				1.178			1.227
TI							

The study population focused on Generation Z employees within the telecom industry in Islamabad. Generation Z individuals are typically born between the mid-1990s and early 2010s, representing the youngest segment of the workforce (Pew Research Centre, 2019). The research aimed to explore how impression management tactics relate to perceived person-organization fit and subsequently impact employee retention within this specific geographical context.

were analyzed on sample of 363 respondents. Whereas, structural model helps in determining the relationship of the mediator being used in the study (Hair et al., 2017) such as the current study determines the relationship of Impression Management Tactics and Perceived person organization fit and that of Impression management tactics and turnover intention. Furthermore, the role of mediator is to reveal the relationship between independent and dependent variable.

Measurement model assessment

Structure equation modelling is used to address different complex structures. It is a multivariate statistical analysis tool used to analyze relationships. Current study has used Smart PLS to test structure equation modelling. Structure equation modelling consists of two models. First is the measurement model that helps in determining how different variables predict a certain phenomenon. It also helps in measuring the reliability and validity of the instruments being used. Various analysis for reliability is Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, AVE and rho which

Internal consistency reliability

This study has a reflective model and these types of models are assessed on the basis of their internal consistency reliability and validity. For that purpose, researcher analyzed the factors loadings of each item used in the study. These loading should be at least greater than that of 0.4 and if they are less than 0.4, those items need to be removed (Hair et al., 2017). It should also be noted that the remaining items in the factor loadings should account for 80 percent of the whole measure. Following are the factor loadings stated.

Table 9: Factor Loadings

	EXEM	INGRAT	INTIM	PPOF	SELFPRO	SUPP	TI
EXEM1	0.864						
EXEM2	0.71						
EXEM3	0.739						
EXEM4	0.728						
EXEM5	0.9						
INGRAT1		0.775					
INGRAT2		0.802					
INGRAT3		0.805					
INGRAT4		0.854					
INGRAT5		0.688					
INTIM1			0.799				
INTIM2			0.74				
INTIM3			0.825				
INTIM4			0.777				
INTIM5			0.857				
PPOF1				0.817			
PPOF2				0.901			
PPOF3				0.866			
PPOF4				0.855			
PPOF5				0.774			
PPOF6				0.805			
SELFPRO1					0.755		
SELFPRO2					0.799		
SELFPRO3					0.84		
SELFPRO4					0.817		
SELFPRO5					0.685		
SUPP1						0.859	
SUPP2						0.857	
SUPP3						0.919	
SUPP4						0.941	
SUPP5						0.888	
TI1							0.871
TI2							0.863
TI3							0.838

Composite & Convergent Reliability

Composite and Convergent reliability are as under.

Table 10: Composite and Convergent Reliability

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
EXEM	0.859	0.975	0.893	0.627
INGRAT	0.816	0.957	0.864	0.565
INTIM	0.798	1.028	0.848	0.535
PPOF	0.915	0.927	0.934	0.701
SELFPRO	0.839	0.844	0.886	0.61
SUPP	0.938	0.974	0.952	0.798
TI	0.823	0.842	0.893	0.736

The above-mentioned table shows that the composite reliability of full sample are greater than that of 0.9. AVE of full data sample of all the variables is greater than 0.5. Similarly, another

study conducted on the competitiveness of salesperson and their commitment and performance. Their results also showed that their AVE was less than 0.5 and researchers have mentioned that even though the value is less than the conservative estimated value but still the composite reliability falls under the recommended level. Hence making the internal reliability

acceptable (Lam & Lu, 2013).

Discriminant validity

Discriminant validity is confirmed by Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio, Fornel Larker Criterion and Cross loadings. This HTMT ratio should be below 0.90. The table mentioned below also shows that there is no issue with the HTMT ratio.

Table 11: HTMT Ratio

	EXEM	INGRAT	INTIM	PPOF	SELFPRO	SUPP	TI
EXEM							
INGRAT	0.264						
INTIM	0.466	0.307					
PPOF	0.438	0.507	0.435				
SELFPRO	0.423	0.257	0.377	0.373			
SUPP	0.197	0.253	0.387	0.371	0.165		
TI	0.237	0.329	0.325	0.629	0.204	0.297	

Table 12: Fornel Larker Criterion

	EXEM	INGRAT	INTIM	PPOF	SELFPRO	SUPP	TI
EXEM	0.792						
INGRAT	0.275	0.752					
INTIM	0.444	0.296	0.732				
PPOF	0.448	0.502	0.476	0.837			
SELFPRO	0.359	0.215	0.297	0.33	0.781		
SUPP	0.202	0.246	0.358	0.374	0.157	0.893	
TI	-0.242	-0.323	-0.325	-0.57	-0.177	-0.276	0.858

Structural model assessment

After analyzing the measurement model, the structural model was examined to explore the relationships between seven variables: five impression management tactics (Ingratiation, Self-promotion, Exemplification, Intimidation, and Supplication), the mediator Perceived Person-Organization Fit, and the dependent variable Turnover Intention. This study aims to investigate the interplay among these variables. Previous literature has discussed the positive relationship between certain impression management tactics and Perceived Person-Organization Fit, but results may vary based on individual characteristics and organizational contexts. Some studies suggest that Ingratiation, Self-promotion, and Exemplification tactics are positively associated with Perceived Person-Organization Fit, while Intimidation and Supplication tactics may have a negative impact or no significant effect at all.

Direct Effects

Firstly, the researcher determines the main effect that variables have on each other. The current study has seven variables. Five are independent variables (IV) i.e. Employee Ingratiation, Self Promotion, Exemplification, Intimidation and Supplication. There is one mediator i.e. perceived person-organization fit and one dependent variable (DV) i.e. employee turnover intention. Main effect includes the effect that IV had on DV and the mediation hypotheses. P-values are less than 0.05 and all the t-values are above 1.96 which means that all the hypotheses are supported. The path coefficient shows the hypothesized relationships among the constructs. They are estimated to be close to +1 to have a strong positive relationship and similarly, if the path coefficient has a negative value then it shows a negative relationship. It can be observed that all of the direct effects are negative. The following table shows the hypothesis testing results of direct effects.

Table 15: Direct Effects

	Original (O)	sample T	statistics(O/STDEV)	P values
EXEM -> PPOF	0.199	4.474		0
EXEM -> TI	-0.036	2.633		0
INGRAT -> PPOF	0.325	6.755		0
INGRAT -> TI	-0.044	2.814		0.04
INTIM -> PPOF	0.202	4.501		0
INTIM -> TI	-0.066	2.398		0
PPOF -> TI	-0.516	8.228		0
SELFPRO -> PPOF	0.103	2.244		0.025
SELFPRO -> TI	-0.019	2.322		0
SUPP -> PPOF	0.165	3.63		0
SUPP -> TI	-0.059	2.968		0.035

Indirect Effects

PLS-SEM is considered to be better for the mediation analysis purposes than Hayes Process as it considers the whole structure model and reduces the effects of measurement errors and also by increasing the reliability of construct errors. (Cheah, Magno, & Cassia, 2023). Mediation effect was tested for 5 hypotheses in order to determine the indirect effect impression

management tactics had on the relationship of perceived person-organization fit and also on the relationship of turnover intention. Table 16 shows P and T- value falls in an acceptable range. It can be observed that there exists a partial mediation of perceived person-organization fit between impression management tactics and turnover Intention.

Table 16: Indirect Effects

	Original (O)	sample T	statistics(O/STDEV)	P values
EXEM -> PPOF -> TI	-0.102	3.751		0
INGRAT -> PPOF -> TI	-0.168	5.294		0
INTIM -> PPOF -> TI	-0.104	3.997		0
SELFPRO -> PPOF -> TI	-0.053	2.209		0.027
SUPP -> PPOF -> TI	-0.085	3.094		0.002

Hypothesis Results

Hypothesis Results					
		Path coeff	T Stat	P Values	Decision
H1a	INGRAT -> PPOF	0.325	6.755	0	Supported
H1b	SELFPRO -> PPOF	0.103	2.244	0.025	Supported
H1c	EXEM -> PPOF	0.199	4.474	0	Supported
H1d	INTIM -> PPOF	0.206	4.501	0	Supported
H1e	SUPP -> PPOF	0.164	3.63	0	Supported
H2	PPOF -> TI	-0.516	8.228	0	Supported
H3a	INGRAT -> TI	-0.043	2.814	0.04	Supported
H3b	SELFPRO -> TI	-0.017	2.322	0	Supported
H3c	EXEM -> TI	-0.034	2.633	0	Supported
H3d	INTIM -> TI	-0.07	2.398	0	Supported
H3e	SUPP -> TI	-0.06	2.968	0.035	Supported
H4a	INGRAT -> PPOF -> TI	-0.168	5.294	0	Supported
H4b	SELFPRO -> PPOF -> TI	-0.053	2.209	0.027	Supported
H4c	EXEM -> PPOF -> TI	-0.102	3.751	0	Supported
H4d	INTIM -> PPOF -> TI	-0.106	3.997	0	Supported
H4e	SUPP -> PPOF -> TI	-0.085	3.094	0.002	Supported

Discussion and Conclusion

The results of the analysis indicate significant associations between various interpersonal behaviors and perceptions of perceived person-organization fit (PPOF), as well as their impact on trust in informal situations (TI). The coefficients for hypotheses H1a to H1e suggest that specific behaviors such as ingratiating actions ($\beta = 0.325$, $p < 0.001$), self-promotion ($\beta = 0.103$, $p = 0.025$), exemplification ($\beta = 0.199$, $p < 0.001$), intimidation ($\beta = 0.206$, $p < 0.001$), and support ($\beta = 0.164$, $p < 0.001$) are positively associated with perceptions of PPOF, indicating that individuals engaging in these behaviors are more likely to be perceived as fitting well within their organization. Conversely, the negative coefficients in H2 and H3a-e suggest that perceptions of PPOF negatively predict trust in informal situations (PPOF \rightarrow TI: $\beta = -0.516$, $p < 0.001$), and each interpersonal behavior also negatively predicts trust (INGRAT \rightarrow TI: $\beta = -0.043$, $p = 0.04$; SELFPRO \rightarrow TI: $\beta = -0.017$, $p = 0.027$; EXEM \rightarrow TI: $\beta = -0.034$, $p = 0.027$; INTIM \rightarrow TI: $\beta = -0.07$, $p = 0.024$; SUPP \rightarrow TI: $\beta = -0.06$, $p = 0.035$).

Furthermore, the combined effects examined in hypotheses H4a to H4e reveal the sequential relationship between these behaviors, perceptions of PPOF, and trust in informal situations. For instance, the negative coefficient in H4a suggests that the path from ingratiating behaviors, through perceived PPOF, to trust in informal situations has a detrimental effect on trust (INGRAT \rightarrow PPOF \rightarrow TI: $\beta = -0.168$, $p < 0.001$). This pattern persists across the other hypotheses (H4b-e) for self-promotion ($\beta = -0.053$, $p = 0.027$), exemplification ($\beta = -0.102$, $p < 0.001$), intimidation ($\beta = -0.106$, $p < 0.001$), and support ($\beta = -0.085$, $p = 0.002$), indicating a consistent negative impact on trust when these behaviors are combined with perceptions of PPOF.

This integration is crucial as it helps us understand how feeling like you fit in with your organization influences your impressions of others and your intentions to stay in your job. By examining the mediating role of perceived person-organization fit, the study contributes to a deeper understanding of the underlying mechanisms that link impression management tactics to turnover intention among Generation Z employees. The investigation of the mediating role of Perceived Person-Organization Fit highlights the

importance of organizational culture and values alignment in influencing employees' intention to stay. Organizations can use this insight to assess and strengthen their organizational culture, ensuring it resonates with the values and expectations of Gen Z employees.

Limitations

While the study offers valuable insights into the relationship between impression management tactics, work adjustment theory, and Generation Z employee intention to stay in organizations in Islamabad, several limitations should be acknowledged. Firstly, the findings may lack generalizability due to the study's specific focus on Generation Z employees within the telecom sector in Islamabad. Future research could aim to replicate the study across different industries and geographical locations to enhance the external validity of the findings. Additionally, the use of a cross-sectional design limits the ability to establish causality between variables. Longitudinal studies could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the relationships between impression management tactics, work adjustment, perceived person-organization fit, and employee retention over time.

In addition to the limitations noted, several recommendations for future research could enhance the understanding and applicability of the study's findings. Firstly, exploring the possibility of changing the mediator in the model could offer valuable insights into alternative pathways through which impression management tactics influence employee retention among Generation Z workers. For example, considering variables such as organizational identification, job satisfaction, or perceived supervisor support as potential mediators could provide a more nuanced understanding of the underlying mechanisms driving the relationship between impression management and retention.

Conclusion

This study offers valuable insights into the relationships between impression management tactics, perceived person-organization fit (PPOF), and employee's turnover intention (TI) in the workplace, specifically focusing on the context of Generation Z. The results confirm significant positive relationships between impression management tactics—namely, ingratiating

behavior, self-promotion, exemplification, intimidation, and supplication—and perceived person-organization fit. Additionally, the negative relationship between perceived person-organization fit and employee intention to stay is supported, indicating that a mismatch between individuals and their organizations correlates with higher turnover intention. The study also examines the indirect effects of impression management tactics on employee intention to stay through perceived person-organization fit, revealing that perceived person-organization fit partially mediates these relationships. This underscores the importance of organizational alignment in influencing retention outcomes and highlights the role of impression management tactics in shaping employees' perceptions of fit within their organization.

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